

Contribution of Temple in Cultural Development of Mohol Taluka

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Introduction

Mohol is a taluka in Solapur district. Temples in Mohol taluka are playing an important role in social and cultural development. As gods and goddesses are important in human life , every village has temples of different gods and goddesses. People from different castes and Classes come together and participate happily in the festival of these gods and goddesses . At this place they come together and mingle with each other with devotion. Various programs are organized through Yatra and festival. People participate in it and show their culture. It adds to the cultural development of the taluk. In that sense, this research paper has studied the contribution of the temple in the cultural development of the taluk. Throwing light on the cultural life of the taluk Some of the talukas The temple has been studied.

Nagnath Temple at Vadaval

It is not seen that Mahanubhava and Nagesh sect spread in the same way as Warkari sect spread in Solapur district. There could be various reasons for this. Of these As the Nagesh Sampradaya is associated with the village of Vadval in Mohol taluka. This sect is known as Vadval Siddha Nagesh Sampradaya. In that regard, Nagnath Devasthan at Vadwal is a very important place.¹ In this sect, Nagnath, the Siddha Purusha, is considered as Gurusthani. The literary production of the Nagesh sect begins with the unknown Siddha. He is known as Adya Acharya of Nagesh sect. Later they settled at Vadaval in Mohol taluka. Although the spread of this sect is less , the Nagnath temple at Vadaval in the taluk is considered as a very important religious place of the Nagesh sect.² The Nagnath temple at Vadwal was built by a wealthy merchant named Ghogare from Vairag. It is mentioned that it was built in 1730 A.D.³ This temple was built during the reign of Bajirao the Elder and is regarded as a masterpiece of Maratha temple architecture. Nagnath Yatra festival is held every Amavasya of the year and thousands of people from Solapur and surrounding areas come to Vadwal to see Nagnath. A major pilgrimage to this shrine is held on Chaitra Shuddha Poornima, which comes after Gudi Padva. People of all castes and religions participate in this annual yatra festival. The form of Yatra is generally on Chaitra Poornima, oil is poured to the deity , kalas is offered. On Chaturthi, the palanquin of Mohol Nagnath God comes to Vadaval and both the Gods meet. After that, garlands are brought from Mohol before departure of Saptamis Gana. After that the worship of God is performed. People keep those garlands in their grains with great faith. Predictions are made on the same day. Also at Khargatirtha both Gods reunite. After that, Ashtamis Mohol's palanquin leaves for return. On Akshaya Tritiya, the Mohol Nagnath Yatra of Chaitra Amvasyas begins after the Vadval God's chhatra moves to Mohol. From historical point of view,

Khargatirtha is Pushkarani of Nagnath temple. Such Pushkaranis are seen around Hindu temples for performing religious rituals. Kharga Tirtha Pushkaranis are made of cut stones and the other part of Pushkarani is carved with images of various gods and goddesses. Ovaras can also be seen in Khargatirtha. There is an arrangement to sit in this overa and worship after bathing.⁴ Thus the temple of Nagnath of Vadval can be seen adding to the cultural splendor of the various Angani Mohol talukas.

Sri Krishna Temple , Vadaval

Like the Nagnath temple, the Lord Krishna temple at Vadawal is important. In this regard , a story is told among the people that while a Nagnath devotee was staying at Hegarus Vadwal and serving Nagnath, his kula deity was attracted to the deity of Shri Krishna temple of Gopalpur. Seeing his devotion to Krishna for his disciple, Nagnath brought the Shri Krishna temple of Gopalpur along with the idol to Vadaval. This temple is of the Yadav period and two parts of the temple namely assembly hall and sanctum sanctorum can be seen. The Sabha Mandapa has twelve pillars and in the sanctum sanctorum there is a black stone idol of Shri Krishna , which is quadrangular. One can also see Shri Krishna holding a flute and a cap on his head.⁵ Nagnath Temple , Mohol

Nagnath temple at Mohol is famous like Nagnath temple at Vadwal and it is an important place of Nagesh sect. This temple belongs to the Yadav period and there are lamp posts near the entrance of the temple. The entrance of the temple is built in black stone and inside the cave can be seen. These two temples of Nagnath divided into sections , there is a meeting hall on sixteen pillars , while in the sanctum sanctorum there is a brass Makhar , a five-faced Shivlinga, and a human brass mook of Nagnath is mounted on it. The gabhara of this temple is octagonal and lotus shaped.⁶

Bhaneshwar Temple , Mohol

The Bhaneshwar temple at Mohol is a Shiva temple and the entrance to the temple is on the east side. Also this temple is the Hemadpanti style.⁷ Stone steps have to be crossed while entering inside the temple. There are many scattered around the stone steps. There is an idol of a Hindu deity near the stairs leading to the temple. The woman appears to be heroic.⁸ A stone semicircle surrounds this Shiva temple. And Kamashil and Mithunshil are engraved on it. At the bottom of the entrance gate, the gatekeepers, Yaksha-Yakshini are carved. The pillars of the temple appear to be of the Chalukya period. Much of the temple was destroyed during the Muslim era. But during the Yadav period, an attempt has been made to save this temple by reviving the temple. A pillar near the entrance to the temple is carved with hawthorn sculptures, an important feature of the Yadav period.

Bhairavnath Temple , Ankoli.

Sri Kshetra Ankoli is famous for Bhairavnath Temple. Bhairavnath is one of the Kal Bhairavnaths and his form is mild. A small gabhara is built on the place where Bhairavnath's pind is located and in the next part of the gabhara, the assembly hall and 64 overs have been built by Ghogare, a Vairag merchant. The top of the temple is domed and has four minarets on all four sides. Overhang in the temple. It is used for the shelter of devotees and for religious work. At the front of the temple is the darshan mandap which is 45x33x18. The temple has a 25 feet tall lamp and today devotees light the lamp and witness the supernatural appearance of the temple.⁹ The Yatra of Bhairavnath Temple at Ankoli is famous and thousands of devotees come from outside for the Yatra. On the occasion of the Yatra, cultural programs and spectacular wrestling of wrestlers are also organized. On Chaitra Vaidya 30 the temple is washed clean with water. On that day at four o'clock in the afternoon, a feast is organized by carrying gulal, camphor, coconut, and incense to the deity. The yatra concludes with the meal with all devotees.¹⁰

Parameshwara Devasthan , Parameshwar Pimpri.

This is a famous roadside shrine in Kurul village, Kamti on the Solapur-Pandharpur road in Mohol taluka. Sadguru Budharam Maharaj has contributed a lot for the development of this temple. This temple is of ancient times and it is Jagurt Devotion¹¹. Even from Mahabharata period this temple is famous and there is an idol of Swayambhu Shankar. This temple, which was small earlier, was developed from the year 1952 with the cooperation of Budharam Maharaj and public participation. The Yatra to the Lord's temple is celebrated on Mahashivratri. Same as the daily program Ashadhi

Poornima here Chaturmas begins and ends on Kartik Poornimas. Budharam Maharaj's death anniversary is celebrated by the temple committee. An important contribution is also made in the social work on behalf of Panch Committee of Parameshwara-Pimpri Devasthan. The marriages of the poor from the new by villages are conducted at a moderate cost and on occasion for free.¹²

Temples at Korvali

Korvali village is situated on the border of Maharashtra and Karnataka. In this village, there are numerous monuments of history, temples with fallen idols, come on, The village also has an inscription of the Yadava period. Korvali village also has a beautifully destroyed Shiva temple of the Northern Chalukya period. Most of this temple has been destroyed but the sanctum sanctorum is in good condition. There are many beautiful works of art on the outer wall of the sanctum sanctorum. Hence this village is known as Sursundari's village Korvali.¹³ On the outskirts of Korvali village on the road to Bijapur is a ruined Narasimha temple. An inscription is placed in this temple. As this handwriting is broken, the text is not clearly mentioned. However, it must be an inscription of the time of the Yadava king Ramachandradeva. From this it can be seen that during the period of Ramchandra Dev Yadav, his officers reached Korvali village. Another famous temple in Korvali village is the temple of Amogasiddha. This temple is called Amogasiddha Shankar temple. These are also images of Sursundarari on the temple.¹⁴ Palkhas from Maharashtra and Karnataka visit this deity on the occasion of pilgrimage to this temple. Also, in Korvali villages, along with this temple, Vitthal temple, Ganesha temple, Ambabai temple and Bodhle Maharaj Math can be seen. On the occasion of Guru Nanak Jayanti, Kartik Poornima is celebrated as a grand celebration of Bodhle Maharaj. This festival lasts for five days. During this time there is a big program of Dahi Handi. Other cultural programs are organized during the celebration of Bodhle Maharaj. In this way, Korvali village is doing an important job of adding to the cultural sector of Mohol taluka. It is preserving the cultural history of Mohol taluka.

Other temples in Mohol taluk

In Mohol taluka there are many famous temples in other villages along with the above temples. Every village has a temple of Maruti. Apart from this, there are of temples of various gods and goddesses in villages in Mohol taluka. These temples are playing an important role in the cultural development of the taluka. In this Chandramouli Ganesha Temple, Mahadev Temple at Papri, Hanuman Temple at Yevati, Ram Temple at Aundhi, Vitthal-Rukmini Temple, Sri Siddheshwar Devasthan Shetphal, Angarsiddh Devasthan Angar,

Kunti Mata Temple at Kothale, Sri Siddheshwar Devasthan at Sohale, Khandoba Devasthan and Chenneshwar Temple of Patkul, Siddheshwar Temple Narkhed, Sri Nagnath Devasthan at Degav (Waluj) , Many temples include Sri Zakaraya Devasthan at Yenki, Yallama Devi Temple at Dhok Babbulga , Ambabai Temple at Bhoyre, Bhairavanath Temple at Ekurke etc. Like this temple, many villages have Mahadev temples. Most of the temples are Hemadpanthi style. As Mohol taluka is close to Pandharpur taluka, Warkari sect has a great influence on the taluka. Therefore, one can see Vitthal-Rukmini temples in some villages of the taluka. Like this Hindu temple, there are also Jain temples in Mohol , Penur , Patkul , Angar, Ashti villages of the taluka. These various temples and shrines are adding to the cultural glory of Mohol taluka.

Such different shrine yatras , festivals in Mohol taluka are celebrated by the people of the village with great joy and thereby expressing their faith in God. The yatras that follow these religious places visit many religious places in the taluk and outside the taluk during festivals. Since each village has a village deity, the villagers who are out of the village for work come to the village on the occasion of the Yatra of their clan deity and village deity to participate in the festival of this village deity and participate enthusiastically in the Yatra festival. Cultural programs such as pageants , plays , dances , bhediks , goddess songs , folk songs and wrestling bouts are organized in the villages in accordance with this religious festival. At the same time , an attempt is made to enlighten the people through intellectual lectures , Shahiri programs of Shahirs. Through this, efforts are being made to preserve Indian culture in the taluka. come on Stalls and shops that fill up during the yatra and festival also generate huge financial turnover. It also benefits them financially. Thus the village temples are adding to the cultural glory of the taluk along with economic benefits.

References:-

1. Gosavi R.R.Paach Bhaktisampradaya, Pune, 2008, Pg.174.
2. Dhere R. C., Navadhara of Ancient Marathi, Moghe Publications, Pune, 1972, Pg. 116.
3. Solapur District Gazetteer, 1997, Pg. 414.
4. Moholkar V.S. (Ed.), Nagesh Darpan, Solapur, December 15, 1991. Pg. 28.
5. Ibid, pg. 12.
6. Ms.Swarali Chandrakant Kulkarni, Unpublished Dissertation, A Qualitative Study of Medieval Historical Monuments in Solapur District , (1206 to 1818 A.D.), July 2008, Pg. 210.
7. Solapur District Gazetteer , Year 1997, Pg. 414.

8. Prof.Waghmare Sanjay Tukaram,Unpublished Dissertation, Diversity of Virgals in Solapur District,2011,Pg.76.
9. Pujari Dattatraya Pandharinath, Sri.Bhairavanath Devasthan Pujari Sri.Bhairavanath Mahatm, (Sri Kshetra Ankoli), Pandharpur, Chaitra Vaidya Shake, 1918 Pg. 3-5.
10. Interview , Shivaji Tukaram Pawar , Villager Ankoli , Dt. 05/ 02/2013.
11. Kulkarni Ushatai Madhavrao , Biography of Sadguru Budharam Maharaj , Parameshwara-Pimpri , Ta.Mohol , Pg. 10.
12. Interview, Mr. Tatyaba Limbaji Pujari, President , Parameshwar Pimpri Devasthan Committee , Dt. 05/01/2013.
13. Mrs. Aklujkar Lata , Sculpture Beauty of Solapur District , Shilp Publications , Solapur, 2013, Pg. 17-18.
14. Ibid, Pg. 7.
15. Golden Jubilee Maharashtra's Glorious Mohol Taluka , May. 2010, Pg. 9.